

The Effect of Some Banana Peel Extracts on the Growth of Brown Oyster
Mushrooms (*Pleurotus cystidiosus* O.K Miller)

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Currently, mushrooms are quite popular among the people. Various processed mushrooms such as crispy mushrooms, mushroom seasoning, and others can be easily found in the market. Especially the oyster mushroom, which has so many benefits for the health of the body, has been widely cultivated by the community. However, oyster mushrooms with brown color variations are not widely known and cultivated. Nutrients containing lignin and calcium can support the growth of brown oyster mushrooms. By using banana peel waste extract as a source of growth nutrients, it is expected to be able to support the growth of brown oyster mushrooms.

Based on the fruit body, oyster mushrooms can be divided into several types, for example, white called *Pleurotus ostreatus*, red called *P. flabellatus*, gray called *P. sajorcaju*, and brown called *P. cystidiosus* (Pasaribu, 2002). Brown oyster mushroom with the Latin name (*Pleurotus cystidiosus* O.K Miller) is a mushroom that has a higher vitamin B, C and D content than other types of mushrooms. Seswati *et al* (2013) added that brown oyster mushrooms have several advantages, namely the fruit body is thicker, can be stored longer, and has a better taste than other types of oyster mushrooms. On average, oyster mushrooms contain 19-35% more protein than rice (7.38%), or wheat (13.2%). There are nine types of essential amino acids found in oyster mushrooms from 20 types of amino acids that resemble protein derivatives produced from animal meat (Meinanda, 2013).

According to Masefa *et al* (2016), it was stated that the addition of lime to the growing media could accelerate the growth of the brown oyster mushroom mycelium. This is due to the presence of a macro element Ca which can function as an enzyme activator, so that the mycelium growth will take place faster because of the enzyme activator contained in the lime. The addition of lime aims to stabilize pH which will also affect the chemical reactions that will take place during the fungal growth process such as cellulase enzyme activity which will degrade cellulose and produce simple sugars (Merisyah, 2014). The results of this study became a source of inspiration to obtain alternative elements of calcium contained in lime from materials that are not widely used by the community or even become waste in the surrounding environment.

Until now, banana peels are still a waste that is thrown away by the community. Without knowing that the banana peel contains elements that are good for the growth of oyster mushrooms, such as carbohydrates, calcium, fat, protein, phosphorus, iron, vitamins, and water. Supriyadi (2007) stated that there is 15% potassium and 12% phosphorus in plantain peel, where these elements can be used as a source of nutrients needed by the growth and production of oyster mushrooms. Confirmed by Maiza et al (2019) which stated that the main structural components of banana peels are cellulose about 75%, lignin about 20.21%, and fiber about 5.1%. Lignin is a material that contains relatively high carbon compared to cellulose and hemicellulose.

According to Rahma et al (2017), the rapid vegetative growth of fungi can be due to the suitability of the substrate nutrition during growth in addition to the high genetic characteristics of mycelium reproduction. In addition, the mushroom growing media decomposed quickly and evenly so that the nutrients contained in the media could be well absorbed by the fungus. To increase growth and production, oyster mushrooms require a variety of specific nutrients. One of the specific nutrients that oyster mushrooms really need is minerals. These mineral elements include macro elements such as Ca (calcium) and Mg (magnesium).

Ashari's research (2007) showed that giving nutrition of banana peel waste extract with a concentration of 20% (10 ml of EKP mixed with 40 ml of water) gave the best results in the mushroom growth process and also increased the production of white oyster mushrooms. The banana peel used in this study is a mixture of several types of bananas. In this study, we will compare the effect of 4 types of banana peels on the growth of brown oyster mushrooms, namely Ambon bananas, Barangan bananas, Raja bananas, and Kepok bananas. Observations were made on the mycelium growth rate, fruit body weight and fruiting body cap diameter.

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